

POLITICAL SCIENCES

FURTHER PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN THE CONTEXT OF POLITICAL COMMUNICATION IN RUSSIA

Eisaev M.B.,

Master's student,

Financial University under the

Government of the Russian Federation

Sukharev M.A.,

Master's student,

Financial University under the

Government of the Russian Federation

Scientific adviser: **Rodionova M.E.**

Candidate of Sociological Sciences, Associate Professor

Abstract

The article analyzes the social media market in the context of political communications. Social surveys, data on social media coverage, data on the popularity of various topics on different social networks, as well as other digital data obtained from social networks were analyzed. In particular cases related to the blocking of social networks and the creation of domestic analogues were analyzed. The authors concluded that social networks in the Russian Federation will only gain popularity, displacing traditional media. Telegram, being the only major social network that was unblocked after being blocked due to the start of a special military operation in Ukraine, has become one of the main channels of political communication in social media. As a result of the analysis, trends in the social media market in the Russian Federation were highlighted: the decline in the number of available social media, the withdrawal of part of the audience from control, the growth of Telegram as a channel of political communication, turbulence in the social media market in the Russian Federation. Based on these trends, one of the scenarios for the development of social media in the context of political communication in the Russian Federation was suggested.

Keywords: social media, political communications, Telegram, VKontakte, WCIOM, Mediascope.

Traditional media are losing their positions and gradually fading into the background. Thus, according to WCIOM, the consumption of printed products has significantly decreased over the past few years. In 2014, 77% of Russians read printed periodicals, and in 2017 already 55% of Russians. And the share of Russians who would prefer an electronic version instead of a printed one increased from 29% (2013) to 47% (2018), and 46% would prefer printing (from 58% in 2013). [1]

The number of daily Internet users is growing. According to WCIOM data, in 2011 28% of Russians used the Internet daily, and already in 2020 the number of daily users began to reach 69% of Russians. [2] At the same time, the population uses both wired and mobile Internet. Despite the fact that initially the Internet was wired, now a larger number of Russians use mobile Internet, and this is especially clearly seen in the villages. [3]

From 2015 to 2021, according to WCIOM-Sputnik database, the number of people using television as the main source of news about events in the country decreased from 62% to 42%, while the number of people using the Internet (social networks, blogs and news, analytical and official sites) increased from 32% to 41%. At the same time, it is worth noting that the older generations use television as the main source of news, and the younger ones use the Internet. Thus, in the group of respondents aged 45-49, 49% used television,

and in the group of 25-34, 60% of respondents preferred the Internet as a source of information.

Social networks and messengers are one of the main sources of information today, especially for the younger generation. For example, according to the Deloitte study "Media Consumption in Russia – 2021", the younger generation tends to receive news on social networks, while older people prefer to receive news from official sources on the Internet.

In addition to analyzing the results of simple social surveys, we will use the results of the study Mediascope which is based not on social surveys like those described earlier, but on analysis using their own measurement tool – «Cross Web». [4] In fact, this is a study of the behavior of research participants on the Internet. A special application collects their Internet activity, while taking into account both mobile traffic (only on Android) and traffic from desktop computers. And, according to their recent research of social media activity in Russia we can have some more detailed information about structure of social media consumption. [5,6]

The beginning of a Special Military operation in Ukraine on February 24, 2022, profoundly affected social media in Russia. Practically all social networks were used to discredit both the armed forces of the Russian Federation and to discredit the government itself, as well as to deliberately spread false information for the psycho-emotional oppression of the population and sowing widespread panic. Each social network reacted

differently to the mass appearance of attempts to misinform the population. VKontakte and Odnoklassniki actively deleted such materials after user complaints, however, platforms such as Facebook and Instagram became mouthpieces of russophobia, allowing not only to publish materials inciting hatred towards Russians, but such materials were also advertised in social networks themselves, so that even a user subscribed only to his friends had every chance to meet with shocking content. In such advertising publications, extreme cruelty towards Russian soldiers was often demonstrated. [7]

Telegram reserves the status of a special media, after the story of its blocking and further unblocking in Russia. Today, in Telegram, you can find a channel with absolutely any agenda, both pro-Russian and pro-Ukrainian, and the state does not pay attention to it. The situation with YouTube is like Telegram's, but there are some nuances, since YouTube blocks official channels associated with the Russian government [8], but there was no reaction to such actions (only statements) from the authorities. YouTube disabled the ability to advertise anything on its site for the Russian audience to suppress the actions that took place on Instagram and Facebook. The social network Tik Tok has solved the problem radically, completely suspending the possibility of publishing new content. [9]

So, according to Mediascope, the average daily coverage of social media has changed as follows (from February 2022 to October 2022): VKontakte – from 38% to 43%; YouTube – from 38% to 41%; Instagram – from 31% to 7%; TikTok – from 27% to 25%; Telegram – from 22% to 38%; Odnoklassniki – from 16% to 16%; Facebook – from 7% to 1%.

It is worth noting quite interesting facts, so, for Telegram, two events became catalysts for audience growth – the beginning of a special military operation in Ukraine and the announcement of partial mobilization in Russia. At the same time, the Telegram audience over the age of 24 is subscribed mainly to news and political channels, the younger audience is subscribed to entertainment channels and news channels related to bloggers. Facebook and Instagram blocking by Roskomnadzor has reduced only the Facebook audience to almost zero, while Instagram remains, albeit with a reduced audience by almost 4 times. However, it is worth noting that after blocking, VPN services have become popular, which make it difficult to obtain reliable data. In YouTube, the structure of search queries by category for October 2022 looks like this: Music – 19%, Entertainment – 18%, Children's – 12%, Videogames – 11%, Serials – 9%, Socio-political – 8%, Cinema – 6%, Shows – 6%.

Almost all the categories were fairly stable during the period from January to October 2022, except for the socio-political category, interest in this category reached high values in March (13%) and in September (9%).

In connection with the above statistics, it becomes obvious that there is a need to study social media both

in general and in the context of political communication. This need is especially aggravated due to its constant variability and development. However, despite the decline in the popularity of traditional media among the population, they cannot be completely denied as a channel of political communication since they continue to be effective. [10]

Further we will define some trends in overall development of social media in the context of political communication in Russia:

- **Reducing the number of available platforms**

Instagram and Facebook blocking, the suspension of the publication of new videos in TikTok lead to a reduction in competition in the social media market. There are no popular domestic alternatives other than Facebook. And accordingly, it is simply impossible to organize the transition of the author and his audience to another platform without alternatives. This is one of the reasons why Instagram still has an audience despite being blocked.

- **The departure of the audience out of control**

Due to the blocking of some social networks, as well as other various news sites, the popularity of VPN services that allowed to bypass the blockages increased many times. Due to the mechanism of VPN, it is much more difficult to determine Russian traffic, both to third-party researchers and to the platforms themselves.

- **The explosive growth of Telegram as a political information channel**

Telegram has long been earning a reputation as an independent platform for communication. As soon as Telegram began to gain popularity among Russian users, it was blocked by a court decision in the spring of 2018. [11] This happened because of the FSB's requirement to provide encryption keys to access user correspondence to combat terrorism and extremism. And there really were prerequisites for this, since the FSB claimed that the terrorist attack in St. Petersburg was being prepared with the help of Telegram. [12] Telegram was building an image of a secure and private messenger, and such conflicts with the authorities only strengthened it. [13] And this image has been strengthening for two years, since Roskomnadzor's attempts to block Telegram blocked everything from the Google search engine to random sites, except Telegram. In 2020, the official departments of the Russian government began using Telegram, for example, the operational headquarters for the fight against coronavirus, to publish official information. And in June 2020, Roskomnadzor announced the lifting of restrictions. [14]

And in 2022, Telegram's coverage has almost doubled. At the same time, the main content in Telegram is news and analytics, and only then entertainment. This can be seen from the structure of the topics of Telegram channels in the Mediascope study.

Pic. 1 – Structure of Telegram channels by theme.

At the same time, it is worth noting that Telegram remains outside the control of the Russian government, at least publicly. It is also necessary to clarify that the category «News» can be equated with «Politics», since Mediascope did not quite correctly define the line between dry news and politics. For example, the channel of the famous blogger «Mir Segodnya with "Yuri Podolyak"» was classified as «News», although the channel is engaged in covering the events of its own, and with their analytics. And the channel «Topor 18+» is engaged in covering events of a domestic scale, unlike the channels «Live Broadcast» or «Before everyone. Well, almost».

• Turbulence in the social media market in Russia

The overflow of a part of the audience from blocked platforms to Vkontakte gave the platform more resources for internal development, besides, Vkontakte itself encouraged the transition of authors to itself. Instagram and Facebook blocking messages were accompanied by various statements about the creation of domestic alternatives. The Yappy analogue of TikTok turned exactly one year old on December 2, but the indicators of social activity, in the form of views, likes, comments, are several times lower than even TikTok, which is in anabiosis. The situation with the analogous applications of Instagram - YARUS and Now is similar.

The problem with domestic analogues is that it is more convenient and more profitable to use methods of bypassing blockages. The end user is primarily interested in the diversity of content, and the author is interested in the number of subscribers. Both are available in blocked social networks, even though they are blocked. At the same time, domestic applications do not attract people due to the small number of authors. In fact, this is a vicious circle: no readers – no authors – no content – no readers. Against this background, there is an opportunity for the growth of domestic platforms, with proper promotion and sufficient funds.

But in the social media market in Russia, YouTube and Telegram are literally a wall, which are not under Russian jurisdiction, and as a result, have the opportunity to violate Russian law and not be responsible for

it. YouTube removes channels associated with the Russian government, for which there were threats of blocking, but the service is still available, and there are no plans to block it. However, apparently, due to the fact that political content is popular there only due to high-profile events, and the rest of the time YouTube is used as an alternative TV, blocking will not follow.

Based on the above trends, an approximate scenario can be assumed for development of social media in the context of political communication. Telegram – candidate for monopolization of the market of political communications in social media in Russia. According to TGstat, Telegram now has 945 political channels (from 10,000 subscribers) in the Russian segment with a total audience of 62 million people, on average, the channel has 65 thousand subscribers. [15] According to the Medialogy, in August 2022, in the top 20 Telegram political channels by views 11 of them were channels of the officials or journalists of traditional media. [16] VKontakte cannot boast of this, often the pages of officials in VKontakte are maintained by their teams, and not by them personally, which leaves an imprint on the audience's desire to follow such pages.

Telegram has taken a special role in political communication in modern Russia, primarily because of its nature, which combines both a messenger and an aggregator of news and opinions. VKontakte could not occupy such a niche, due to the peculiarities of the algorithms for forming the news feed. Elite communication takes place in Telegram, so, one example of such is the criticism of the General staff of the armed forces of the Russian Federation by Ramzan Kadyrov [17]. It is worth noting that the article on RBC refers specifically to the publication in the Telegram channel.

Telegram channels can be news sources for other media, while the channel itself does not have to be authorized [18]. This entails unpredictable consequences, since even in the top 20 channels of the political Telegram, you can see anonymous channels spreading false information to a wide audience (for example, the Telegram channel "General SVR"). Telegram has not become, and is unlikely to become, a mass media outlet for the whole country or even for most of it in the near future. First, this is due to the fact that, despite the large

number of Telegram users, not everyone reads Telegram channels, this can be seen based on the number of subscribers and views of Telegram channels. However, as a means of political communication, Telegram proved to be successful.

In addition, Telegram for an ordinary user is a source of some specialized knowledge that is not available in ordinary social media. Various channels telling about the "secrets of the Kremlin" or simply analyzing the current situation attract readers. Oleg Lyakhovenko in his article «Telegram Channels in the System of Expert and Political Communication in Modern Russia» concludes that: "Despite the objective predominance of manipulative content, telegram-channels form a special expert ecosystem, a kind of "distributed think tank" which analyses Russian internal political and international agenda in real time" [19].

However, Telegram also has disadvantages, for example, the president of the communication holding "Minchenko Consulting" Evgeny Minchenko concludes that the future of Telegram belongs to authorized, not anonymous Telegram channels [20]. But Eugene Stulova, the executive director of «Minchenko Consulting», in her work "The Four Horsemen of the Information Apocalypse" talks about the phenomenon of a new reality in which trust by an anonymous source of information literally turns this information into true: "Another phenomenon of the new reality is the trust in anonymous sources of information. An example of this is the Telegram messenger channels. Anonymous authors publishing allegedly insider information cannot be verified, however, they acquire hundreds of thousands of subscribers, the media begin to refer to them — as a result, they leave the virtual space and begin to live in the real one" [21]. And at the moment, a fairly significant part of Telegram is occupied by anonymous channels, and because of Telegram's foreign jurisdiction, the authors of such channels remain unpunished for Russian justice.

VKontakte remains a platform primarily for entertainment content, just like YouTube. However, due to the fact that the authors of these platforms have a much greater credit of trust among the audience due to the fact that they are often not anonymous, as in Telegram, they also have a certain potential for political communication. In addition, VKontakte allows you to launch various advertising campaigns with the possibility of accurate targeting, when Telegram targeting is extremely inaccurate, and YouTube advertising is disabled. In addition, back in 2017, it was noted that the popularity of VKontakte as a political communication channel is growing rapidly, both from the electorate and from political PR specialists [22].

The localization of social media, and as a result, the displacement of some authors and their audience from the media space, due to the application of various laws related to fakes, discrediting of the Armed Forces of the Russian Federation, LGBT propaganda, foreign agents, etc., will not lead to the purification of the Russian information space. The situation will only worsen, because virtual enclaves of people of different views, incompatible with the law, but living on the territory of

the Russian Federation, will be created due to the availability of tools to bypass the blocks.

It seems quite real that there will be no appearance of a domestic analogue soon, since those analogues that exist now are uncompetitive, despite the blockages. The case with Rossggram, which was promised to launch on March 28, spoiled the reputation of analogues, but now it is still in development. And the launch of analogues while there is an access to their originals is initially a losing strategy since the clone will always be in the role of catching up. However, the emergence of a new social network offering a unique way to communicate is quite realistic.

References

1. WCIOM. The Age of Digital Media: Paper versus Screen: <https://wciom.ru/analytical-reviews/analiticheskii-obzor/epokha-czifrovyykh-media-bumaga-protiv-ekrana>
2. WCIOM. Life online: consumption, use, entertainment: <https://wciom.ru/analytical-reviews/analiticheskii-obzor/zhizn-onlain-potreblenie-polzovanie-razvlechenija>
3. WCIOM. The Internet as a sphere of Russian human habitation: <https://wciom.ru/analytical-reviews/analiticheskii-obzor/internet-kak-sfera-obitaniya-rossiiskogo-cheloveka>
4. Mediascope. Mediascope has launched a new Internet measurement project - Cross Web: <https://mediascope.net/news/1434615/>
5. Mediascope. Social Media: https://mediascope.net/upload/iblock/5ab/8bh9sab0ioqdvufiv52lhw3ccruhq585/%D0%9D%D0%A0%D0%A4_SocialMedia_%D0%A1%D1%83%D0%B0%D0%BD%D0%BE%D0%B2%D0%B0_11.11.22.pdf
6. Mediascope. Media audience https://mediascope.net/upload/iblock/d6a/qqk514ramn101f86r82qt9o9e91flihp/%D0%9D%D0%B0%D1%82%D0%B0%D0%BB%D1%8C%D1%8F%20%D0%91%D0%BE%D1%80%D0%BE%D0%B7%D0%B4%D0%B8%D0%BD%D0%B0_Mediascope_011222.pdf
7. RIA News. Instagram has been blocked in Russia: <https://ria.ru/20220314/instagram-1777974202.html>
8. RBC. Google blocked the Federation Council channels on YouTube: <https://www.rbc.ru/politics/18/10/2022/634e5a889a79470dcacd7a87>
9. Kommersant. TikTok banned streaming and uploading new content to users from Russia because of the law on fakes: <https://www.kommersant.ru/doc/5249513>
10. Nigmatov A. S. (2021). Social media in political communications. *Communicology: Electronic Scientific Journal*, 6(4), 41-51.
11. RBC. Why the authorities decided to unblock Telegram. The main thing: https://www.rbc.ru/technology_and_media/18/06/2020/5ee211609a79473d9eccbc4c

12. RBC. The FSB announced the preparation of a terrorist attack in the St. Petersburg metro using Telegram: <https://www.rbc.ru/politics/26/06/2017/595096cd9a794764bd8674c5>
13. GQ. How Pavel Durov came up with Telegram and why you should not trust the messenger: <https://www.gq.ru/heroes/rozenberg-telegram>
14. Roskomnadzor. About Telegram Messenger: <https://rkn.gov.ru/news/rsoc/news73050.htm>
15. TGStat. Telegram channels search: <https://tgstat.ru/channels/search>
16. Medialogia. Political Telegram Channels: August 2022: <https://www.mlg.ru/ratings/socmedia/telegram/11474/>
17. Kadyrov linked the withdrawal of troops from the Estuary with "army nepotism": <https://www.rbc.ru/politics/01/10/2022/6338496c9a794741143b8966>
18. "Polituprava": Russia recognizes LDPR in case of aggression by Ukraine: <https://regnum.ru/news/polit/3509377.html>
19. Lyakhovenko, O. (2022). Telegram Channels in the System of Expert and Political Communication in Modern Russia. *Galactica Media: Journal of Media Studies*, 4(1), 114-144. <https://doi.org/10.46539/gmd.v4i1.230>
20. Novye Izvestia. Evgeny Minchenko: "Telegram is already competing with TV": <https://newizv.ru/interview/07-11-2017/evgeniy-minchenko-v-rossiyskih-kommunikatsiyah-telegramm-uzhe-konkuriruet-s-televizorom>
21. Eugene Stulova (2021). *The Four Horsemen of the Information Apocalypse: a brief guide to reputation management policy in the new information reality*. ISBN: 9785907470613
22. Ermolaev V. P. (2017). The VKontakte social network as a modern channel of political communication. *Society and power*, (3 (65)), 63-73.